

THE ROLE OF TEACHING LISTENING SKILL FOR NON-PHILOLOGICAL STUDENTS THROUGH INTERNET RESOURCES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: the given article illustrates the issue of using Internet resources in teaching English, which contribute to the development of Listening skills. Particular attention is paid to the aspect of improving the listening skills of students of non-philological faculties.

Keywords: listening skills, language material, assimilation, TED talks, speech activity.

According to the existing information, for a long time Listening skill was considered an aspect that educators did not pay due attention to when teaching a foreign language. This was explained by the fact that students' listening skills are automatically developed by immersion in the language environment and practice, while working with grammatical, lexical and phonetic material. At present, students need to develop a high level of proficiency in the process of listening, as they themselves want to learn to understand what they are told in English in person, at business meetings, on television, in the theater, when watching movies, traveling to foreign countries, listening to audio recordings, etc.

Listening skill is considered to be the most difficult aspect in mastering the English language. This difficulty is explained by overcoming such factors as the nature of the language material, presentation conditions, semantic content, sources of information, as well as individual characteristics of the speaker (manner of speech, pace, accent) and the listener, his auditory experience, and many others. On the other hand, listening is a powerful tool for teaching a foreign language, since it contributes to the assimilation of the lexical composition of the language and its grammatical structure, makes it possible to master the sound side of the language being studied, its phonemic composition and intonation: rhythm, stress, melody. In one of his latest publications, M. Rost described listening as "a necessary type of speech activity, because it provides the listener with information. Without understanding the information, no learning can begin...". It should not be forgotten that listening, along with speaking, provides the possibility of communication in a foreign language. Without mastering the ability to distinguish foreign speech by ear, communication with representatives of other cultures is impossible in principle. Unfortunately, with two or three academic hours of English per week, the teacher fails to pay due attention to the development of students' listening skills. Increasing emphasis is placed on independent work, which became possible thanks to the emergence of Internet resources. For instance, consider some of them in detail:

1. BBC Podcasts. BBC radio stations have a wide range of topics that, in the absence of subtitles, will be useful to listen to as a kind of background, which will put the listener in a state of "flow" and create the illusion of "total immersion" in an authentic environment. Due to the feeling of a "flow" state, the forgotten knowledge of grammar and vocabulary begins to activate on its own, and the melody of the language itself is captured, which is also important when teaching speaking. It is worth noting here that in such radio programs as, for example,

BBC Learning English - 6 minute English , the podcast hosts are native speakers, so it is possible to listen and learn a living language, in the form in which it is used by ordinary residents English-speaking countries, then 260 authentic material is used. Podcasts are divided into 3 levels: the first one is for beginners (elementary), the second one is for students with average knowledge of English (lower intermediate and intermediate), the third one is for students with above average knowledge (upper-intermediate). The advantage of the BBC Learning English project is that the rate of speech of voiced dialogues is different, depending on the level of language proficiency.

2. TED (Technology, Entertainment, Design) is a universal online platform with many conferences of leading experts in the field of science, art, design, politics, culture, business, global issues, technology and entertainment. The mission of the conference is to disseminate unique ideas ("ideas worth spreading"). Recordings of the most well-known speakers can be found on the official TED.com website. Currently, more than 1500 selected lectures with translations into different languages are available on the website. All videos are published under the Creative Commons BY-NC-ND license, which allows their free distribution . The system for working with such a site, as with any other audio text, is reduced to the following scheme: "sound - text - sound" (♫ + T + ♫). First, students are invited to watch a video without subtitles and catch the main point. This is followed by a detailed analysis of the text with the help of the subtitles presented, as well as, if the teacher wishes, with the help of additional exercises on vocabulary and grammar. After that, the video is watched again, during which auditory-visual synthesis takes place, simultaneous broadcasting of sound and image (with subtitles or with a text that has just been analyzed), which contributes to the development of skills and abilities of listening to speech and stimulates oral-speech communication of students, further discussion of the video can be made.

4. In 6 Minute English there are inserts from dialogues in English from BBC correspondents, in addition, there are explanations of new English words and expressions. Please note that all explanations are given in English only. Moreover, scripts are attached to the podcasts (text version of the transmission). It should be emphasized that many foreign language learners do not realize that when they listen to their native speech, in fact, they do not listen to every word, moreover, they underestimate the fact that a person closely links linguistic knowledge with existing experience and knowledge of such concepts like theme and culture. Faerch and Kasper point out that the absolute understanding of the audio text is an erroneous representation of how the natural process of perceiving information in the native language takes place. The effort to understand everything does not lead to effective results causes a feeling of fatigue and, ultimately, leads to failure.

Conclusion To sum up the results, it is necessary to teach students to select the necessary information, ignoring the irrelevant, i.e. to teach them to do it the way they do it in their native language. The main thing is to develop the skill of guessing, to learn to predict what could be discussed, what the speaker could say in a given situation, thus leveling possible gaps in perception. Internet resources are an effective means of organizing the educational space, support social relations, as they allow participants in the learning process to carry out joint activities, use the latest materials in various formats, and also train various types of speech activity. Authentic educational audio material is interesting, informative, meaningful, and comprehensible, corresponds to the modern reality of a foreign-speaking society and creates

favorable conditions for students to master new regional information, speech behavior of native speakers, contributes to their acquaintance with the living language, the life of the people, its culture, modern realities.

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